

Cyber-feminism activities in the digital era: Confronting the violence against women in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of digital communication has transformed how feminist movements engage with social issues and mobilize collective action. In Bangladesh, social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter have become important spaces for raising awareness about gender-based violence and promoting women's empowerment. However, the nature and impact of these online feminist activities remain insufficiently examined. This study aims to explore the emergence and trends of cyber-feminism in Bangladesh and to assess its role in resisting violence against women (VAW) through digital engagement. A qualitative approach was adopted, drawing on key informant interviews with feminist activists and content analysis of relevant social media discussions. This combination provided insights into both the experiences of digital activists and the patterns of online feminist discourse. Findings reveal that cyber-feminist activities in Bangladesh are largely centered on social media and contribute positively to awareness building, public accountability, rapid response to incidents, and increased women's participation in social and economic initiatives. Nevertheless, challenges such as misinformation, misuse of online spaces, limited digital literacy, and unequal access to technology continue to hinder broader progress. The study highlights that cyber-feminism in Bangladesh represents a dynamic yet contested form of digital activism. It underscores the need for greater digital literacy, stronger policy implementation, and conceptual clarity around online feminist movements. The research contributes to understanding how digital spaces can both empower and constrain feminist activism in developing contexts, offering directions for future studies and policy initiatives.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber-feminism represents a contemporary strand of feminist thought that emphasizes the intersection between feminism, cyberspace, and technology. It can be understood both as a philosophy and as a community of practice. In essence, cyber-feminism is feminism situated within cyberspace—the informational realm made possible through electronic circuits and computer networks (Vitanza, 1995). In

other words, cyberspace encompasses the digital domains where computers, modems, satellites, and telecommunication systems facilitate social interaction, collectively known as the internet.

In Bangladesh, cyber-feminist movements have emerged in response to the expanding influence of the internet and digital technologies. Feminist activists and advocates have recognized the transformative potential of online spaces to amplify women's voices and challenge gender inequality. Social media platforms, blogs, and online forums have become vital arenas for feminist engagement, enabling activists to share information, mobilize support, and advocate for women's rights.

Globally, digital platforms—particularly social networks—have played a crucial role in the evolution and expansion of feminist movements. Campaigns such as *Ni Una Menos* in Argentina (2015) and *Me Too* in the United States (2017) illustrate the profound impact of digital activism in mobilizing collective voices. These movements have fostered cultural change and influenced public policy, but they have also coincided with a notable increase in online gender-based abuse over the past five years.

Such abuse manifests in multiple forms, including cyberbullying, identity theft, the unauthorized publication of personal data, smear campaigns, defamation, online extortion, legal intimidation, and coordinated attacks laced with xenophobic, racist, and sexist rhetoric. These hostilities particularly target communicators, activists, and human rights defenders, undermining their freedom of expression and participation in public discourse—ultimately affecting the health of democracy itself. In Bangladesh, women engaged in advocacy experience digital platforms as both spaces of empowerment and arenas of systemic harassment.

A recent study from Latin America and the Caribbean reports similarly concerning trends, showing that online gender-based abuse significantly restricts women's freedom of expression. Reports by UN Women and the Follow-up Mechanism of the Belém do Pará Convention define such abuse as gender-based harm facilitated through information and communication technologies. UNESCO further emphasizes that online violence often extends into the offline world, underscoring its real and lasting consequences. Attacks on women communicators, politicians, and human rights defenders reflect a gendered pattern of aggression against those who dare to make their voices heard.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study examines the intersection of technology use, women's empowerment, and violence against women within the specific context of Bangladesh. The term cyber-feminism was first introduced in 1994 by Sadie Plant, founder of the Cybernetic Culture Research Unit at the University of Warwick, United Kingdom. It refers to feminist efforts to theorize, critique, and engage with the Internet, cyberspace, and emerging media technologies. Emerging from the "third wave" of feminism—which followed the "second wave" of the 1970s that emphasized equal rights—cyber-feminism also draws from the "first wave" of the early twentieth century that focused on women's suffrage and political participation.

Donna J. Haraway played a pivotal role in shaping the theoretical foundation of cyber-feminism through her influential essay *A Cyborg Manifesto*. She envisioned a socialist, feminist cyborg as a metaphorical figure that challenges fixed identities and resists systems of control that marginalize women and other oppressed groups. Haraway emphasized the importance of women becoming technologically competent, engaging critically with the "informatics of domination," and navigating these systems strategically and politically.

In the evolution of cyber-feminist thought, early advocates such as Sadie Plant argued that women and the Internet share intrinsic characteristics as non-linear, self-replicating systems built on connection and communication. She viewed digital spaces not as male-dominated by nature but as arenas where women could redefine identity, experiment creatively, and claim autonomy beyond traditional social boundaries.

However, other scholars—including Susan Luckman and Anna Munster—have critiqued the overly optimistic assumption that technological participation alone can empower women. They argue that technologies are embedded within historical and structural power relations, and that women's empowerment requires more than access; it necessitates critical engagement with the sociocultural and political dimensions of technology. Furthermore, critics note that many early cyber-feminist perspectives failed to account for disparities in access to technology, particularly among women outside privileged, Western, and middle-class contexts. A more inclusive framework must therefore acknowledge the diverse realities of women across economic, geographic, and cultural divides.

Empirical studies (Mahpara, 2022; Nova, 2019; Sultana, 2021) have discussed the empowering potential of technology for women, though most focus on its negative aspects, such as cyber-violence and online harassment. Few have examined how digital engagement might reduce violence against women or foster

empowerment through cyberspace. This gap highlights the need for further research connecting digital participation with women's agency and social transformation in contexts like Bangladesh.

Technological advancement is increasingly recognized as a defining feature of the "fourth wave" of feminism due to its multidimensional potential. As global trends show, cyber-feminist activism manifests through various forms of online engagement. Radhika Gajjala and Yeon Ju Oh identify twenty-first-century cyber-feminism across blogging networks, online conferences, gaming communities, fandom spaces, social media platforms, and digital mothers' groups advocating for social issues such as breastfeeding. They also emphasize the emergence of cyber-feminist spaces led by women in non-Western and marginalized communities, demonstrating the global reach and diversity of the movement.

Drawing on these theoretical and empirical foundations, this study explores the evolution and impact of cyber-feminist activities in Bangladesh, particularly through social media platforms. It investigates how Bangladeshi women use online campaigns, hashtags, digital storytelling, and advocacy to resist gender-based violence. The research also offers a comparative perspective by examining global trends in cyber-feminism and digital activism.

The study anticipates that active engagement in cyber-feminist movements correlates with a reduction in violence against women, emphasizing the transformative potential of digital activism. It further posits that women's empowerment is closely linked to technological participation and innovation. Ultimately, integrating feminist approaches within digital spaces may contribute to building a more inclusive, equitable, and empowered society for women in Bangladesh.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study draws upon cyber-feminism, feminist media theory, and the digital activism approach to analyze women's resistance activities in online spaces. Among these, cyber-feminism serves as the central theoretical foundation. Emerging in the 1990s, cyber-feminism conceptualizes cyberspace as a political arena where feminist ideologies can be redefined and expressed through technological innovation (Plant, 1997). It underscores the potential of digital environments to challenge patriarchal structures, expand access to information, and amplify the voices of marginalized groups. Within this study, the framework is used to examine how women in Bangladesh employ online platforms to resist and respond to gender-based violence.

Feminist media theory complements this perspective by situating women's digital participation within broader socio-cultural and power relations. As Gill (2007) notes, this framework helps to explore how gendered experiences shape women's engagement, representation, and visibility in media spaces. Applying this lens allows for an understanding of how Bangladeshi women's online activism interacts with—and sometimes contests—the cultural, religious, and social norms of their environment.

The digital activism framework, developed by Mendes et al. (2019), further informs the study by analyzing how social media enables collective feminist action. It provides insight into the ways digital technologies facilitate organization, mobilization, and solidarity across local and global contexts. Drawing on this approach, the present research situates Bangladeshi cyber-feminist practices within a global framework while foregrounding local dynamics and challenges.

4. METHOD

This study adopts a qualitative and exploratory approach (e.g., Toyon, 2023) to understand how women in Bangladesh use digital spaces to express resistance and participate in cyber-feminist activism. A multiple case study design was chosen to capture the diversity and complexity of feminist practices online, particularly in relation to addressing violence against women.

The research draws on two main sources of data: social media content and key informant interviews. Social media was selected because it is one of the most visible and influential platforms for feminist expression in Bangladesh. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and X (formerly Twitter) were reviewed, as these are widely used for organizing campaigns, sharing experiences, and mobilizing collective action. Posts, discussions, and online initiatives that focused on women's empowerment, gender equality, and responses to violence against women were analyzed over a selected period. Both global and local online movements were considered to understand how Bangladeshi activists engage with broader feminist discourses. To complement the digital content, in-depth interviews were conducted with individuals directly involved in online feminist and digital rights initiatives. Respondents included activists, campaign organizers, rights advocates, and content creators. Purposive sampling was used to identify participants with relevant

experience and active engagement in digital advocacy. The interviews explored personal experiences, strategies, challenges, and perceptions regarding the role of digital platforms in advancing women's rights.

All data were analyzed thematically through an interpretive lens. The analysis involved reading the material to identify recurring ideas and patterns. These patterns were then organized into broader themes that captured how women use digital spaces to resist gender-based violence, promote empowerment, and engage in collective action. The analysis focused on meaning, expression, and context rather than measurement, allowing the study to capture the richness of lived experiences.

Ethical considerations guided every stage of the research. Informed consent was obtained verbally from all interview participants, and confidentiality was strictly maintained. Identifying details were omitted, and any online materials used were publicly available or shared with permission. Online content was verified against reliable sources and existing literature to ensure credibility and authenticity. As this study forms part of an ongoing project, the findings are presented in a narrative form, summarizing emerging patterns and themes from both the social media analysis and the interviews. Given the interpretive and human-centered character of the research, a degree of subjectivity is inherent and acknowledged.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Conceptualizing global cyber-feminism movements against VAW

Across the world, a new kind of feminist movement has taken shape—one that unfolds not in the streets or classrooms, but online. Global cyber-feminism represents how women have turned digital spaces into tools of resistance, using social media, websites, and apps to challenge violence, discrimination, and deeply rooted patriarchal norms. It builds on earlier feminist struggles but adapts them to the digital age, transforming technology from something once viewed as distant or male-dominated into a space of collective empowerment.

One of the earliest and widely recognized moments that revealed both the power and danger of the online world was Monica Lewinsky's return to public life through her 2015 TED Talk. Branded for years as a target of public humiliation, she revisited her experience to expose the cruelty of online shaming and the long-lasting effects of digital harassment. Her story marked a turning point—it reminded the world that the internet is not just a tool for expression but also a terrain where gender-based violence plays out in new forms. Lewinsky's case became symbolic of how online spaces can simultaneously harm and empower, pushing feminist thinkers and activists to rethink how to confront misogyny in virtual environments. At the same time, women across continents began using social media to tell their own stories of harassment and exclusion. What started as individual posts often grew into large, connected campaigns. The conversation around street harassment is one such example. For a long time, it was brushed aside as something women simply had to tolerate. But when one woman shared her experience online, others followed—creating a wave of testimonies that made invisible violence visible. Initiatives like *HarassMap* in Egypt, *Chega de FiuFiu* in Brazil, and *Hollaback!* in the United States took this further by using mapping technologies to record incidents of harassment and expose its everyday nature. These digital efforts challenged social complacency and reframed public harassment as a serious human rights issue, not a passing inconvenience.

Technology has also become a direct lifeline for women facing violence. In Brazil, the PLP 2.0 app linked victims of domestic violence with the police, serving as a panic button that could be activated in emergencies. Elsewhere, *Justice Adda's FemMap* created an online space where activists and organizations could share resources, coordinate campaigns, and exchange strategies for promoting gender justice. Through such tools, the feminist movement has grown into a global network—one that learns from local struggles and adapts them to new contexts.

Taken together, these examples show that cyber-feminism is more than a series of online campaigns. It is a rethinking of how feminist action operates in a world defined by technology. It views cyberspace not just as a communication tool, but as a social and political space where women can reclaim visibility, challenge systems of control, and build solidarity across borders. Global cyber-feminism, in this sense, is both a continuation and an expansion of feminist history—one that reflects how activism itself is evolving in the digital age.

5.2. Social media's revolutionary role in addressing socio-cultural stereotypes Worldwide

Across the world, social media has opened new avenues for people to share experiences and participate in conversations that were once difficult to access. Noethless, in many societies, women's voices have long been overlooked or discouraged in public spaces. The rise of digital communication has started to bridge

this gap, offering platforms where women can express opinions, share stories, and question social norms more freely.

Access to information has been central to this change. Through online platforms, women can learn about their rights, opportunities, and challenges faced by others in similar contexts. This connection often builds confidence and collective understanding, allowing more women to challenge stereotypes that have persisted for generations. In many ways, social media functions not only as a communication tool but also as a space where ideas about gender and equality are negotiated and redefined.

Several global examples reflect how online discussions have influenced awareness and public debate. After the 2012 Delhi incident, the hashtag *#DelhiGangRape* became a rallying point for conversations on women's safety, prompting widespread attention in both digital and traditional media. Likewise, campaigns such as *#StandWithPP* in 2012 showed how online communities could express solidarity and influence institutional decisions within a short time. Across platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter, women's organizations and individuals continue to use digital spaces to share knowledge, mobilize support, and connect across borders. The growing presence of women bloggers and online creators has also encouraged younger audiences to engage with gender issues in more open and creative ways. Traditional media, in turn, often draws from these online conversations, giving them a wider reach.

All in all, these trends suggest that social media has become an important space for dialogue and reflection. By making women's voices more visible and by encouraging participation in public discussions, it is gradually reshaping social perceptions and challenging stereotypes in diverse cultural contexts.

5.3. Digital activism and cyber-feminist practices in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, digital activism has become an increasingly visible and important form of social engagement. Women and feminist groups are using online spaces not only to raise awareness but also to question the deep-rooted social and cultural attitudes that shape their lives. Platforms such as Facebook and Instagram have become tools for expression, allowing women to speak openly about issues like gender-based violence, workplace harassment, and body image—topics that are often avoided in traditional (offline) public discussions. Hashtag movements, short videos, and digital storytelling have turned into ways of connecting and mobilizing people across different regions of the country.

Cyber-feminist practices in Bangladesh have taken shape in many forms. Some activists focus on spreading information and resources about online safety and digital rights, while others create spaces for discussion through blogs, podcasts, or live sessions. These efforts have helped many young women find a sense of belonging in communities where their voices are heard and respected. Online campaigns that highlight stories of resilience or protest against abuse have encouraged more women to step forward and share their experiences. This everyday engagement—posting, commenting, sharing, and organizing—has gradually built a culture of digital participation that extends feminist ideas beyond academic or institutional spaces.

However, this growth has not come without difficulties. Many women who take part in online activism face harassment, doxing, or character attacks that reflect broader gender biases in society. The fear of being targeted discourages some from speaking out, especially those without strong social or institutional support. In response, women's groups have developed their own coping strategies—strengthening privacy measures, supporting one another through informal networks, and reporting online abuse when possible. Several organizations now conduct training on digital literacy and cyber security, helping activists understand both the risks and the tools available to protect themselves.

What makes Bangladesh's cyber-feminism distinct is its diversity. The women who participate in these spaces come from different regions, religions, and economic backgrounds, each bringing their own perspectives on what empowerment means. For some, online activism is a way to claim professional identity or creative freedom; for others, it is a lifeline to solidarity and survival. This diversity adds complexity to the movement but also makes it richer and more grounded in the lived realities of Bangladeshi women.

Altogether these practices show that cyber-feminism in Bangladesh is not a single movement but an evolving set of responses to everyday challenges. It is shaped by both opportunities and constraints—by access to technology, by social attitudes, and by women's determination to claim their place in digital spaces. Despite ongoing risks, the persistence of these efforts signals a quiet but powerful shift: women are increasingly using the digital world to assert their presence, share knowledge, and imagine new possibilities for equality and connection.

5.4. Collaborating with global movements for change

Bangladeshi cyber-feminists are gradually more connecting with international feminist networks, sharing ideas, and learning from global experiences while bringing their own perspectives to these discussions. These collaborations have helped activists exchange practical strategies on issues such as online safety, gender equality, and women's digital rights. Alongside this, many groups in Bangladesh are engaging in policy discussions and advocacy, pushing for stronger laws against cyber violence and promoting digital literacy so that women can use technology with greater confidence and security.

Cyber-feminism in Bangladesh also links closely with efforts to increase women's participation in technology and entrepreneurship. More women are now involved in online businesses, digital training, and creative industries, showing how technology can open new opportunities for independence and visibility. Yet, the digital world also carries risks. Many women face harassment, data misuse, and online abuse, often without clear legal protection. Respondents noted that such experiences can spill over into real life, causing stress, insecurity, and withdrawal from online spaces. Even with these challenges, the digital movement in Bangladesh continues to grow. Through collaboration, creativity, and persistence, women are finding ways to make technology work for them—building networks of support and linking local activism with global conversations about empowerment and change.

5.4.1. Policy advocacy

Cyber-feminist activists in Bangladesh are also engaged in policy advocacy aimed at influencing laws related to gender equality, online safety, and digital rights. Some groups work specifically to promote legislation addressing online harassment and cyber violence against women. Others focus on education—particularly on improving digital literacy, online safety, and responsible internet use among women and girls. These initiatives help women navigate the digital landscape with greater confidence and security.

5.4.2. Promoting tech inclusion and women's entrepreneurship

Cyber-feminism in Bangladesh also intersects with broader initiatives promoting women's participation in technology and entrepreneurship. Efforts to close the gender gap in STEM fields and to encourage women's involvement in the tech industry have gained momentum. This dimension of cyber-feminism supports not only gender equity but also national development goals.

5.4.3. Advancing technological empowerment

Technology-based initiatives in Bangladesh aim to advance women's empowerment by fostering economic, social, and political inclusion. Entrepreneurial ventures, mentoring networks, and online training programs help women develop skills and access opportunities. The digital divide is gradually narrowing, allowing women greater access to information and the ability to participate more fully in public life.

5.5. Challenges and risks in the digital sphere

While the digital sphere has created new spaces for empowerment, it has also introduced significant risks for women. Cyber-harassment, defamation, and online abuse have become widespread, often targeting women more intensely and leaving them vulnerable to psychological harm and social stigma. Respondents in this study highlighted that the anonymity of the internet allows perpetrators to act without accountability, making it difficult to trace or prevent such violence. They also pointed to systemic barriers—such as weak legal protections, inadequate law enforcement, and the underreporting of cases—that hinder efforts to combat cyber violence effectively. In many instances, online threats and harassment extend beyond the virtual realm, leading to real-life consequences and reinforcing cycles of fear and silence. Participants further expressed concerns about data misuse, sexual harassment, hacking, and the spread of misinformation, alongside issues like costly internet access, poor connectivity, and limited digital literacy. These factors combine to create an environment where women's safety and participation online remain precarious. Addressing these challenges requires not only stronger laws and enforcement but also a deeper investment in digital education and awareness to promote safer, more responsible engagement with technology.

5.5.1. Violence against women in cyberspace

The digital realm, initially viewed as a space for empowerment, has also become a site of violence. Cyber-harassment, defamation, and online abuse are increasingly common and disproportionately target women. The anonymity of the internet often emboldens perpetrators, complicating prevention and redress.

5.5.2. Barriers to addressing cyber violence

Efforts to combat cyber violence face major obstacles, including weak legal frameworks, limited law enforcement capacity, and chronic underreporting. The complex and cross-border nature of cybercrimes demands comprehensive strategies that combine legal reform, education, and collaboration among stakeholders.

5.5.3. Overlap between online and offline violence

Online abuse frequently spills into offline life. Threats, harassment, and exposure in digital spaces can escalate into physical violence, reinforcing fear and silence. Addressing cyber-violence is therefore integral to the broader struggle against gender-based violence.

5.5.4. Media influence and digital misuse

Respondents expressed concerns about cyber violence, misuse of personal data, sexual harassment, and hacking, all of which contribute to a sense of insecurity. Many highlighted the financial barriers to purchasing devices and maintaining internet connections, as well as the unreliability of networks. A recurring concern was the potential for involvement in illegal activities online, such as producing explicit content, extortion, spreading misinformation, or engaging in fraudulent schemes.

Participants also mentioned the growing addiction to online entertainment, which often distracts from academic or productive pursuits. The popularity of short-form video content, particularly when influenced by inappropriate material, was also noted. Many attributed these problems to low levels of digital literacy, emphasizing the urgent need for education and awareness to foster safer and more responsible online engagement.

5.6. Patterns of feminist activism in the digital age

Respondents described cyber-feminist activism as a transformative force that exposes and challenges various forms of violence against women. Rooted in social media engagement, these movements have brought attention to issues such as domestic violence, sexual harassment, body shaming, and psychological abuse—topics often silenced in traditional settings. Cultural and religious norms often pressure women to remain silent about such violence, but digital spaces have allowed new forms of visibility and collective action.

Studies, including Zaman and Sayeed (2021), have shown that global online movements such as *#Hashtivism*, *#BlackGirlMagic*, and *#YesAllWomen* have effectively confronted gender discrimination and inspired local initiatives. Similarly, Bangladeshi online activism reflects this broader trend, with participants acknowledging that cyberspace—driven by feminist activities—has the potential to challenge patriarchal norms and reshape gender relations.

While most respondents viewed these developments as positive and empowering, some also voiced concerns. They noted that the absence of strong legal protection and the difficulty of seeking justice often limit the real-world impact of online activism. Nonetheless, the growing use of digital spaces to advocate for women's rights marks an important cultural shift—one where technology continues to reshape how resistance, awareness, and solidarity are expressed.

5.7. Trends of online movements on women's empowerment in Bangladesh

Respondents highlighted that access to information plays a crucial role in women's empowerment. The ability to make informed decisions is a central aspect of empowerment, and cyber-feminist initiatives help women reassess their rights, social status, and personal agency. However, empowerment remains uneven, as financial inequality and limited access to technology restrict participation for many women, especially in rural areas.

Despite these barriers, online movements have inspired many women to speak out, make independent decisions, and claim control over resources. This growing confidence reflects the link between information, autonomy, and empowerment. Studies such as Zaman (2021) have noted how social, cultural, religious, and political factors influence women's participation online, and how misogynistic reactions often attempt to suppress their voices.

Even so, new initiatives continue to emerge. Online campaigns such as *"Do Not Stand Too Close to My Body"* have raised awareness about harassment in public transport, while others have called for policy action, including women-only buses. Broader movements such as *#MeToo* have also influenced feminist dialogue in Bangladesh, encouraging solidarity and open discussion of sexual harassment.

Research by Ahmed et al. (2014) identified a strong need for platforms where women can share experiences and find support. In response, technological solutions such as the JOY and WAB apps were developed to help women and children in emergencies, enabling quick communication with law enforcement or trusted contacts. The government's "Digital Bangladesh" initiative has further supported women's empowerment, particularly through entrepreneurship.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, women's engagement in online business increased substantially. Platforms such as the Women and e-Commerce Forum (WE) helped connect and support female entrepreneurs, while Facebook and Instagram became major tools for small business development. According to data from Meta (2022), over 70% of women-led businesses in Bangladesh were launched on Facebook during the pandemic, with a noticeable rise in women-led enterprises on Instagram as well. The e-Commerce Association of Bangladesh (e-CAB) reported online sales reaching nearly \$2 billion by August 2020, reflecting the significant growth of digital entrepreneurship.

In this evolving context, Bangladesh continues to experience both challenges and opportunities. The country's cyber-feminist landscape mirrors its broader social transformation—complex, uneven, but steadily expanding the space for women's voices, empowerment, and participation.

5.8. Strategic recommendations for strengthening cyber-feminism in Bangladesh

The recommendations presented in this section are drawn from the insights and reflections of respondents who actively engage in online feminist activism and digital rights advocacy. Their perspectives stem from lived experiences in navigating Bangladesh's digital landscape and confronting its challenges. While the suggestions reflect participants' direct observations, they also resonate with broader feminist and digital empowerment frameworks. They emphasize the need for digital literacy, safer online environments, inclusive participation, and supportive policy and institutional mechanisms that can foster women's empowerment in both virtual and real-world spaces.

5.8.1. Accessible digital literacy programs

Implement comprehensive digital literacy programs targeting women across diverse socio-economic backgrounds. These programs should equip women with the skills to navigate cyberspace safely and confidently, fostering empowerment through digital knowledge.

5.8.2. Community-centric cyber-safe spaces

Establish community-based, cyber-safe spaces where women can openly discuss and address issues related to violence. These platforms should provide supportive environments for sharing experiences, seeking advice, and mobilizing collective action.

5.8.3. Localized cyber-feminist initiatives

Encourage localized cyber-feminist initiatives tailored to Bangladesh's socio-cultural context. Align online movements with the specific challenges and aspirations of women in different regions to ensure inclusivity and relevance.

5.8.4. Collaboration with educational institutions

Build partnerships with educational institutions to integrate cyber-feminism into curricula. Incorporating content on women's rights, digital literacy, and cyber-security can help develop informed and empowered students.

5.8.5. Financial inclusion programs

Advance financial inclusion by implementing programs that provide women with access to, and control over, financial resources. Because empowerment is closely tied to economic independence, such initiatives can significantly strengthen women's agency.

5.8.6. Legal awareness campaigns

Launch broad campaigns to raise awareness of existing laws related to violence against women. Improve understanding of available legal remedies and create accessible channels for reporting and addressing cyber-based violence.

5.8.7. Partnerships with the tech industry

Collaborate with technology companies to develop and promote women-friendly technologies and applications. Encourage the creation of platforms that prioritize safety, privacy, and empowerment, and involve women in design and development processes.

5.8.8. Mental health support services

Acknowledge the psychological impact of online violence and provide accessible mental health support. Embed mental health resources within cyber-feminist initiatives so women facing digital abuse can obtain timely care.

5.8.9. Advocacy for policy reforms

Sustain advocacy for policy reforms that specifically address cyber-based violence against women. Work with government bodies to create and enforce laws that safeguard women in digital spaces.

5.8.10. Inclusive media representation

Promote inclusive representation of women in both traditional and digital media. Encourage positive narratives that challenge stereotypes and help reshape societal attitudes, creating conditions more conducive to empowerment

6. CONCLUSION

This study explored how women's movements are evolving in the digital era, particularly through hashtags and online activism that challenge violence against women. In recent years, digital spaces have become vital platforms for women to share their experiences, raise awareness, and mobilize support across communities. In Bangladesh, where gender inequality and violence against women continue to pose deep social challenges, these online movements have opened up new ways for women to participate, speak out, and connect with others who share similar struggles and hopes. The main goal of this research was to understand how digital activism—often described as cyber-feminism—contributes to women's empowerment by expanding access to information, strengthening visibility, and building solidarity. It also sought to explore the barriers women face in using these platforms and the broader influence of online feminist movements on social awareness. Using a qualitative and narrative approach, the study relied on content from social media and insights from activists and digital advocates. Since this is part of an ongoing project, the findings are presented in a narrative form that captures emerging patterns rather than fixed conclusions, recognizing that subjectivity is a natural part of interpreting social realities.

The findings suggest that the rise of cyber-feminism in Bangladesh reflects a global trend where technology is being used as a tool for social change. Women are using digital platforms to document their experiences of harassment and discrimination, challenge social taboos, and advocate for justice and equality. These online efforts have helped create spaces for dialogue and awareness that were previously unavailable or inaccessible. At the same time, challenges remain—such as limited digital literacy, weak internet access, social stigma, and the risk of online harassment—all of which hinder women's ability to participate freely and safely. Yet, despite these obstacles, digital activism continues to inspire solidarity and gives women greater confidence to speak out, organize, and engage in social change.

This study adds to the understanding of how digital spaces can serve as both a site of empowerment and a site of struggle for women. It highlights how Bangladeshi activists are adapting global feminist ideas to local contexts, using technology not only to express resistance but also to imagine new forms of social connection and collective strength. The study offers insight into how online feminist practices are reshaping the conversation around gender and power in both public and private life. The implications of this research point to the growing importance of safe, inclusive, and accessible digital environments. Expanding women's digital literacy, ensuring responsible media use, and encouraging collaboration between institutions and communities can help strengthen the positive outcomes of these movements.

This research, however, has its limitations. The findings are based on narrative analysis and subjective interpretations, which may reflect the perspectives of participants and the researchers' analytical lens. While every effort was made to ensure rigor and reliability, the interpretive nature of qualitative research means that some degree of subjectivity cannot be avoided. Additionally, the events, incidents, and movements discussed in this paper are presented purely for academic purposes and do not indicate any political stance or affiliation. The authors have taken care to maintain neutrality and objectivity throughout, focusing on scholarly understanding rather than political interpretation. The purpose of this work is to contribute to academic discussions on digital activism and its role in shaping gender equality in Bangladesh and beyond. While the study underscores the significance of its findings, it also recognizes that cyber-feminism in Bangladesh remains a developing and underexplored area. Future research might further investigate the evolving potential of cyberspace, mechanisms for ensuring cyber security, and the challenges of combating digital and physical forms of violence against women. It may also examine how feminist

approaches, digital policies, and the preparedness of law enforcement can together strengthen women's empowerment through technology in Bangladesh.

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